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Exploring the role of ICTs and assistive technologies for deaf and hard of hearing students in Greek postsecondary education

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Abstract

This research explores the experiences of deaf and hard of hearing (D/HH) students in Greek postsecondary education, focusing on their attitudes, perceptions, and practices regarding the use of Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) and Assistive Technologies (ATs) for educational inclusion and learning support. Using a qualitative approach, the research conducted 19 individual interviews and 2 focus groups with a total of 26 D/HH students. The findings reveal predominantly negative attitudes towards the current technological infrastructure and policies in postsecondary education, with students often resorting to self-help practices and advocacy to overcome barriers. While ICTs and ATs such as smart devices, captioning applications, and distance learning platforms were recognized as beneficial, participants highlighted significant challenges, including technical issues, lack of Greek language support in many applications, and insufficient understanding of D/HH needs by educators. The study concludes that there is a pressing need for enhanced accessibility, the integration of technological solutions, and the improved preparedness of educational institutions to enrich the educational experience of D/HH students in Greek postsecondary education. Although the institutional adoption of technology is crucial, it alone is insufficient to fully achieve inclusion.

Keywords: Deaf and hard of hearing, information and communication technologies, assistive technologies, postsecondary education

1 Introduction

Education is a right that must be accessible to all, regardless of physical or other limitations, such as sensory hearing disability [1]. Deaf and hard of hearing (D/HH) students encounter unique challenges within the educational system, which require specialized interventions and support [2]. In particular, D/HH students in postsecondary education face multifaceted challenges that extend beyond the limitation of hearing itself [3]. A significant difficulty involves access to information and communication during lectures and discussions, where the use of sign language or lip reading is not always feasible due to the lack of sufficient interpretive services or technological aids, such as real-time captioning [4]. Moreover, certain aspects of the physical environment may be misinterpreted or misunderstood, particularly when poor acoustics or insufficient lighting hinder lip reading, which affects communication between hearing students and D/HH students [5]. Socially, the lack of understanding and existing prejudices can lead to isolation and exclusion, disrupting students' ability to fully participate in the educational community [6]. This highlights the need to enhance the visibility of their experiences [7].

The rapid advancement of Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) and Assistive Technologies (ATs) has significantly supported the improvement of access and quality of life for individuals with hearing disability [8]. Assistive Listening Devices and FM Systems improve auditory experiences by amplifying environmental sounds and transmitting the speaker's voice directly to hearing aids or receivers, thus reducing background noise and enhancing clarity even in noisy settings [9] - [11]. Captioning and Real-Time Transcription technologies provide immediate text conversion of spoken language,

allowing D/HH students to access lecture content instantly and engage actively through accurate and timely transcriptions ^[12, 13]. Remote Learning Platforms and Accessible Text Editing Software, often featuring captions and screen reader compatibility, offer flexible, personalized learning experiences and facilitate collaboration in group work and online discussions ^{[14] - [16]}. Visualization Tools, such as diagrams and mind maps, help students comprehend complex information by making abstract concepts more accessible and fostering interactive learning ^[17]. Additionally, Sign Language Apps, Video Relay Services, and Remote Sign Language Interpretation provide functionalities ranging from learning and translation to real-time interpreter-mediated communication ^{[18] - [20]}.

The integration of ICTs and ATs into the education of D/HH students requires continuous development and adaptation of existing systems to keep pace with technological challenges and user needs ^[21]. Through this process, it is possible to create a more equitable and accessible educational environment that promotes comprehensive and successful learning ^[22]. For hard of hearing students, the use of enhanced hearing systems, such as hearing aids and cochlear implants, is one of the most widely used forms of support ^[23]. There is also a wide range of specialized software designed to assist D/HH students in learning and communication ^[24]. D/HH students possess strong attention skills, but these can be easily disrupted by peripheral visual stimuli, as their hearing loss makes them more susceptible to visual distractions. Simplified navigation and easy access to online material can help minimize these disruptions ^[25]. The development of educational modules within applications through a simplified, step-by-step approach has been widely accepted ^[26]. Information and content should be presented visually, using images, subtitled videos, and sign language, as D/HH individual's process images and videos more effectively than words ^[27].

In Greece, initiatives such as the creation of digital multimedia libraries, online dictionaries, and multimedia e-books integrated into a bilingual framework make learning more accessible and interactive for D/HH students ^[28]. These educational approaches enhance the educational experience by offering tools that promote linguistic and cultural engagement and reduce the risk of linguistic isolation, providing D/HH students with valuable means for successful academic and social integration ^[29]. However, in Greek postsecondary education, inadequate support, inaccessible facilities, and the lack of accommodations, such as sign language interpreters and differentiated instruction, persist. While some challenges have been studied, the full impact of ICTs and ATs on meeting their educational needs remains underexplored ^[30].

The purpose of this research is to investigate the attitudes, perceptions, and practices of D/HH students enrolled in postsecondary education structures regarding the role of ICTs and ATs in educational inclusion and learning support. Specifically, the study aims to capture and interpret their expectations, goals, and perceptions of the possibilities and challenges associated with their academic efforts. Examining the practices adopted by both the students themselves and the educational institutions to support learning, access to education, and social inclusion, as well as identifying the ATs that contribute to their success, is of paramount importance. These considerations, combined

with an exploration of the challenges and obstacles encountered in educational life, are expected to further illuminate the proposals that emerge from research and literature for improving measures of access and equality of opportunities. Within this context, the following research questions are formulated to guide the study:

RQ1: What are the available and utilized ICTs and ATs that support D/HH students in Greek postsecondary education?

RQ2: What are the attitudes, perceptions, and practices of D/HH students toward the educational structures and policies in Greek postsecondary education, concerning the use of ICTs and ATs?

RQ3: What are the most significant technological challenges that D/HH students face in their efforts to adapt and succeed in the academic environment of Greek postsecondary education?

These questions will serve to contextualize the research and offer critical insights into the effectiveness of existing practices, as well as identify areas requiring enhancement to more effectively support D/HH students.

2. Materials and Methods

In the context of this research, ethnographic research methodology was selected to understand the deeper social dimensions, cultural practices, perceptions, and behaviors that shape the educational experience of this population ^[31]. This approach necessitates an in-depth and holistic exploration of the significant subgroup within the Deaf community, utilizing direct observation, participatory observation, and interviews ^[32].

Purposive sampling was employed as the sampling method, which is an effective approach for selecting a sample within this community ^[33]. The sampling process resulted in the selection of 19 D/HH students for individual interviews and 7 D/HH students for 2 focus groups. The total sample of 26 D/HH participants was selected based on the following criteria: (a) experience in postsecondary education in Greece as a D/HH student, and (b) proficiency in Greek Sign Language to facilitate communication during the interviews and focus groups. The sample size was chosen with the aim of achieving an optimal balance between depth of interpretative understanding and practical manageability, ensuring that the research is both reliable and feasible. This decision took into account the availability of participants, the time constraints for conducting interviews and focus groups, the additional time and resource demands associated with communication via sign language, as well as the subsequent management of visual data ^[34].

The interviewees ranged in age from 23 to 45 years old. A higher percentage, 60%, were women, while 40% were men. Regarding hearing disability, the sample included both deaf and hard-of-hearing individuals, with 70% having pursued higher education at universities, Schools of Advanced Vocational Training, Vocational Training Institutes, and colleges, while 30% participated in vocational training programs. The educational institutions attended were 90% public, with the remaining 10% attending private institutions. The majority, 80%, lived or studied in Athens, with the rest describing experiences from other cities. As for language preference, 75% primarily communicated using Greek Sign Language, while 25% used oral communication. Among those using assistive hearing technologies, 30% had cochlear implants, and 70% used hearing aids. Most of the participants, specifically 80%,

came from hearing parents, while 20% had deaf parents. During the interviews and focus groups, Greek Sign Language was used to ensure accurate communication, and all discussions were video recorded and subsequently transcribed. A certified interpreter of Greek Sign Language, ensured effective communication and comprehension of the participants' responses, providing the necessary expertise in the field.

During the data analysis, thematic analysis was employed to extract and categorize the main ideas and themes that emerged from the interviews and focus groups. After the initial coding was completed, the codes were reviewed, and potential themes were identified by grouping related or similar codes into broader categories. This process was grounded in iterative reading and reflection on the data, aiming to uncover underlying patterns and meanings that permeate the participants' narratives [35]. As preliminary themes were identified, the research team finalized them by defining the boundaries and content of each theme [36]. In the final phase of thematic analysis, the identified themes will be verified and validated through a review of the data and the search for further examples to ensure the validity of the findings [37].

The close involvement of researchers with the participants and the creation of a trusting environment that encouraged free expression ensured the validity and reliability of the study [38]. This was achieved through the consistent and systematic application of the same data collection and analysis methods [39]. Additionally, data triangulation enhanced reliability by comparing findings from different sources and methods, such as interviews and focus groups, helping to confirm the data's reliability and reducing the potential for error or bias [40].

Obtaining clear and fully informed consent from all participants is a critical stage in educational research, especially when involving sensitive groups like D/HH students. During the conduct of this study, participants' rights to decline or withdraw from the research at any time were respected. The principles of anonymity and confidentiality were strictly adhered to, ensuring the protection of participants' personal data throughout the research and in all related publications. The principle of transparency was also maintained consistently to ensure that all participants were fully informed of any risks or difficulties that might arise during the research. Moreover, the research respected the cultural uniqueness of D/HH students. Recognizing cultural differences and appreciating the unique characteristics that sensory hearing disabilities bring to education was central to the research. Additionally, all regulations of the European General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) were strictly followed, ensuring the protection and security of participants' personal data.

3 Results

3.1 Available and Utilized Technologies

The majority of D/HH students reported that access to online platforms for synchronous and asynchronous distance learning was a valuable tool for accessing educational material and attending classes. The use of e-class platforms for accessing educational content was particularly beneficial due to the visual nature of the material and the availability of important information such as announcements and course content. For instance, one D/HH student highlighted that because of the focus required and the need for visual contact

with the instructor, they could "focus entirely on the lesson without taking notes, understanding the content during class, and later reviewing the ready-made material on e-class. This has helped me greatly as a deaf person". Another D/HH student remarked, "We receive good service, updates via email, meetings through Zoom, and communication with an interpreter we bring ourselves. We are a separate group in the meetings, and they help us, explain things to us, make corrections, and that way I understand what I need to do".

Among the available ATs, remote interpretation services were noted, particularly during the Covid-19 pandemic, which enabled accessible education. Many D/HH students expressed satisfaction with the convenience of the multifaceted communication offered. One student mentioned that the use of interpreters through Zoom, distance learning, and communication via messages and email significantly improved their educational experience compared to earlier years of study. Another participant highlighted the impact of remote interpretation services, which, although not provided directly by educational institutions, are now being extended into education due to students' initiatives and resources. Emphasizing the need for autonomy, one D/HH student stated, "At the university, I might need to communicate with the administration, and I will make the video call myself to the service, and the interpreter will speak with the administration, but it will be me who is speaking, not my mother, for example. This is very important".

Projectors and visual aids were also used as supportive tools by a group of interviewees, while hearing devices connected to microphones or cochlear implants were identified as critical resources for the accessibility of D/HH students. On the one hand, students benefit from the flexibility and ease of use offered by smart devices, such as tablets. However, on the other hand, they encounter difficulties related to battery limitations, especially during long lectures. A few students shared individual experiences, highlighting the potential support that could be provided by smart glasses with subtitles. Reflecting this sentiment, one student stated, "I have seen glasses with subtitles, and for me, that is important, meaning that a deaf person does not stand out and feels like everyone else in the crowd".

3.2 Attitudes and Perceptions of D/HH Students

The attitudes of D/HH students toward ICTs ATs in educational settings vary significantly. For some, these tools played a supportive role, while for others they were less helpful. In certain cases, ATs were seen as the primary source of support. This highlights the diversity and heterogeneity of experiences among D/HH students when it comes to the effectiveness of such tools. The majority of interviewees expressed negative feelings due to the lack of institutionalized support. This absence leads to frustration, a sense of abandonment, and difficulties in the educational process, with resignation not being uncommon. Emotional responses such as psychological fatigue, sadness, and feelings of being undervalued, anger, and irritation were commonly expressed by the students. Some students noted differences in conditions between two universities, while others highlighted disparities between their undergraduate and postgraduate studies. One student expressed mixed emotions and difficulties related to the absence of technical equipment, particularly for supporting automatic captioning services, which forced them to rely more on self-study.

Another student clarified that the in-person presence of an interpreter is essential, and while the use of technologies to support sign language is seen positively, it does not replace live communication.

Additionally, the interviewees expressed positive attitudes towards the advanced educational systems of other countries, such as Sweden, where access to information was described as seamless, with videos in sign language displayed in educational settings and beyond special education. Similarly, a student mentioned countries like the United States and Germany, where "there is always access everywhere, regardless of whether a deaf student has enrolled or not, especially when deaf students attend a general university".

Regarding the positive aspects of technology use, the value of speech-to-text applications was acknowledged, particularly when they function accurately, providing access to verbatim transcription, which is especially useful in cases of specialized terminology. One student noted, "Some courses, like anatomy which is medical, and physiology, have very difficult vocabulary. How will it be conveyed? By using the alphabet, but that is confusing and stressful". On the other hand, there was a noted need for improvement in the accuracy and support of these technologies in Greek, compared to the more numerous Latin-based applications, leading some students to use English applications or even to give up.

One D/HH student mentioned using speech-to-text technologies occasionally on their own initiative, emphasizing a perspective that combines technological resources with interpretation, a view that was echoed by other D/HH participants. The student stated, "For me, the right approach is to have a microphone with subtitles (speech-to-text) and simultaneously an interpreter, because most deaf people are bilingual-written Greek and sign language-and they are better in one or the other. So, when you are taught using both, the result is that you receive more information and assimilate it more easily".

Regarding visual material, another student emphasized that technology cannot substitute for real-time interpreting, stating, "I don't like it when they write on the board; it is essential to have a projector and the material on the computer. But the material should not have too much text, because it becomes exhausting. However, if there is no interpreter in the room, no technology will help at all". Access to educational material, such as digital slides and notes, and the adaptation of the technological environment to the needs of D/HH students are also considered important factors. Adapted digital educational materials that are designed to avoid overwhelming students facilitate learning. A commonly appreciated practice is the creation of digital content that is concise and clearly articulated, combined with rich visual stimuli. Additionally, establishing breaks every 40 minutes is seen as beneficial to avoid mental fatigue, keeping students focused and productive, especially when using computers and projectors. Clear and articulate speech from instructors, in conjunction with the use of microphones connected to hearing aids, is considered essential for D/HH students who rely on these technologies. In terms of the physical environment, supportive technological factors include a proper setup that allows good visual contact with the instructor and the projector screen, along with adaptations such as front-row seating, good lighting, the presence of microphones, small rooms

with good acoustics, and noise minimization. Another student reported an improved experience in graduate school due to technology, particularly distance learning and interpreting, while another faced adaptation issues due to hearing difficulties and spatial conditions.

Overall, the perceptions of D/HH students were predominantly characterized by disappointment and a sense of isolation, with many difficulties in adaptation, access, communication, and interaction because of the lack of institutionalized support, inadequate policies, insufficient technical equipment such as automatic captioning services, challenges with interpreting services, the absence of seamless access to educational materials, and the physical environment, including poor acoustics and insufficient visual contact with instructors. However, some reported positive experiences and satisfaction when support and access to resources were available or, despite the challenges, due to the occasional assistance and support they received from peers and professors.

3.3 Technological Challenges and Practices of D/HH Students

The lack of accessible ATs and ICT resources for D/HH students was identified as a significant shortcoming by many participants. A common concern among several D/HH students was the need for better technological solutions, particularly speech-to-text applications. The complete absence or inconsistent use of these tools appeared to hinder many students with different linguistic preferences and desires for a combination of resources, highlighting these technologies as essential tools that educational institutions should provide.

In this context, concerns were raised about the ability to engage in dialogue and participate in lectures and activities, the accuracy of transcriptions, the comprehension of written Greek, and the fatigue caused by following subtitles. One student expressed concern, saying, "It's a good idea. But can you follow written text for two hours? It's very tiring for the eyes. I'm not sure if it helps; it might strain your eyes". Similarly, regarding the ability to engage in dialogue, another student mentioned, "Subtitles help me, but how can I respond? I can't respond with subtitles; it can't be done in writing".

Additionally, the lack of provision for smart devices, such as tablets, and the technical difficulties experienced by those who used their own devices-like limited battery life during internships or while on the move-led to feelings of exclusion and frustration. The absence of other technological tools that could have been provided also hindered the educational experience of D/HH students. One student emphasized that it should be the responsibility of the educational institution to ensure the availability of these resources. Another pointed out that any technologies used should be compatible with the simple and affordable devices that most D/HH students typically use. In the same vein, several students mentioned devices and aids that are not widely known and were not encountered during their educational journey.

Moreover, during online classes, D/HH students faced technical issues such as connection disruptions and poor audio and video quality, which hindered their ability to follow the interpreter and participate in the course effectively. Specifically, one student reported difficulties with video calls during online classes, particularly with remote interpretation, to the point that they stopped using

this method for accessing lectures, except in a few cases as a last resort. The student noted, "In all the classes, I couldn't manage at all. It was very tiring for the eyes, a lot of hassle. So, I canceled that method. Only in one or two classes".

D/HH students often adopt adaptive practices based on the recognition of the absence or inadequacy of technological support resources. Some students actively sought out support services while also turning to self-directed learning. One student remarked, "If I don't have the information I need, I can find another way, like asking hearing classmates what was said. Yes, there is always another way, but it depends on the deaf person wanting to find it. You always have to search for a solution". One D/HH student emphasized the necessity of optimal environmental conditions regarding sound and lighting, while another highlighted the importance of the student's own efforts combined with the understanding of others. This student noted, "I insist, I fight. I think, what can I do? Can I get a better hearing aid? Can I get a microphone, can I do something, an app? Yes, okay. But the other person also needs to help". These practices demonstrate the resilience and adaptability of D/HH students, as well as the importance of collective advocacy, environmental adjustments, and the need for mutual support in educational settings. This underscores the urgent need for educational institutions to provide more reliable, compatible, and comprehensive solutions to support the learning of D/HH students effectively.

4 Discussion

The comparison of data from international research in the field with the findings of this study vividly highlights that despite the progress made in postsecondary education in Greece, significant technological barriers persist in the educational journey of D/HH students. International studies have demonstrated successful implementation of assistive technologies and inclusive practices in countries like the United States and the United Kingdom^[41], underscoring the gap in Greece's educational system. The findings reveal that while there is a wide variety of perceptions among D/HH students regarding the educational technological infrastructure and policies in postsecondary education, many students hold negative views. These negative perceptions are largely shaped by inadequate support, communication challenges, exclusion from information, and difficulties in understanding the material. Research has shown that adequate support systems positively influence D/HH students' perceptions and academic outcomes in other educational contexts^{[42], [43]}.

Moreover, this negative perspective is further influenced by the lack of other accessibility provisions, such as the provision of interpreters, institutional support from educational structures and educators, as well as the overall limited implementation of inclusive education practices in Greece. International policies and case studies where the provision of sign language interpreters and institutional support have significantly improved inclusion for D/HH students highlight the importance of these services^{[44], [45]}. Although some aspects of the policies may offer benefits, the overall evaluation of accessibility and inclusion remains negative, indicating that existing policies fail to meet the diverse needs of the students. This contributes to feelings of isolation and uncertainty, which ultimately affect their educational experience^[46].

In this context, the practices adopted by D/HH students include personal solutions such as using written notes, self-teaching, and seeking help from peers. Studies discussing similar coping mechanisms among D/HH students internationally emphasize the effectiveness of institutional interventions in reducing reliance on personal strategies^[47]. At the same time, D/HH students evaluate the technologies and support services in postsecondary education with mixed feelings. While they acknowledge the positive impact of smart devices and applications, as well as cochlear implants and hearing aids, they also face daily technical problems, such as the low accuracy of automatic captions, the lack of support for the Greek language in most technological applications, and the absence of appropriate devices provided by educational institutions that meet specific technical requirements. International research on the benefits and limitations of technological aids reflects similar challenges and the need for ongoing development^[48]. Additionally, the inability of technology alone to fully address the communication, educational, and learning needs of D/HH students becomes evident, particularly in the absence of professional interpreters provided by educational institutions^[49].

Comparative analysis between this study's findings and international literature reveals parallels that underscore the role of technology as a supportive tool in enhancing accessibility and participation of D/HH students in the educational process^[50]. Nevertheless, international literature frequently portrays a more optimistic picture regarding the implementation of educational inclusion for D/HH students^[51], whereas the findings of this study indicate that, within the Greek educational context, D/HH students continue to confront significant obstacles. Similarly, although international literature emphasizes the importance of technology as a supportive tool for enhancing accessibility and participation in education, documenting a wide array of applications and supportive technological options^[52], D/HH students in Greece seem to lack access to most of these applications. They rely almost exclusively on speech-to-text software or distance learning platforms. Even in these instances, however, D/HH students highlight the necessity for personal initiative and improvisation to bridge gaps in technological support and to ensure compatibility of technologies with their personal devices.

5 Conclusion

The attitudes, perceptions, and practices of D/HH students regarding the ICTs and ATs provided by educational structures and policies in postsecondary education in Greece are predominantly negative. This negativity is particularly evident in response to the insufficient provision of supportive technologies and services that ensure equality and access. Although there are isolated instances of positive experiences due to support from professors and peers, D/HH students generally find themselves compelled to adopt self-help practices and advocate for support to complete their studies. This situation leads to feelings of frustration, confusion, uncertainty, anger, sadness, and a sense of abandonment.

D/HH students recognize the value of using ATs in their educational process. Portable smart devices, captioning applications, synchronous and asynchronous distance learning platforms, and social media are considered extremely helpful. Additionally, the use of cochlear

implants and hearing aids significantly improves the educational experience for those who use them. However, students also point out several negative aspects, such as technical problems with smart devices, limited internet access, low accuracy of automatic captions, and the lack of Greek language support in many speech-to-text applications. Similarly, D/HH students feel that professors in postsecondary education often lack sufficient understanding of their needs, which leads to inadequate technological support or even resistance to using such tools.

In conclusion, the low ratings of technological accessibility and inclusion by many students indicate that current policies do not meet their needs. Their perceptions included strong feelings of isolation, devaluation, and uncertainty, which negatively affect their educational experience. It appears that D/HH students are not choosing but are instead forced to adopt self-help practices, advocate for support, and take on roles of self-organization and collective action to overcome barriers and succeed in their studies.

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